

THE EFFECTS OF TETRACYCLINE USAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE *E. COLI*

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Abstract

This journal article investigates the relationship between the use of tetracycline antibiotics in poultry farming and the development of antibiotic-resistant *E. coli* infections in humans. Data on tetracycline use in livestock from the ESVAC database was compared to data on resistant *E. coli* infections from the WHO GLASS database for 19 countries. The analysis found no correlation between tetracycline use and resistant infections. However, a slight correlation was seen between general antibiotic use in livestock and resistant infections. While the research aim was not fully achieved due to lack of data on specific poultry antibiotic use, the results still indicate health risks from overuse of antibiotics in farming.

Keywords: Antibiotic Resistance, Tetracycline, *E. Coli*.

1. Introdução

The excessive use of antibiotics represents a global issue for the pharmaceutical industry, due to antibiotic resistance being a constant topic evaluated as a worldwide crisis. There is a global effort to reduce the use of these medications, due to the risk of not having enough antibiotics to neutralize the rising generations of resistant bacteria. This also applies to farming, where there is a concern to reduce the use of antibiotics aiming to stop the development of resistant bacteria in livestock that could be transmitted to humans. This theme was chosen priorly by me and my supervisor because my aunt is a member of the Ethics Committee on the Use of Animals (CEUA) and specialized in the regulation of poultry farming, which helped clarify doubts and concerns about the theme, making the research process much easier.

The investigation focuses on exploring how different countries regulate dosage and control the amounts of

tetracycline, one of the most common antimicrobials in farming and one of the antibiotics which *E.coli* is most resistant to.

1.1 Hypothesis

Is notable that the intensive use of tetracycline ia with the medical cases originated from resistant *E. Coli* . These two data sets when analyzed adjacently can result in a correlation between the deaths caused by AR (antibiotic resistant) *E. Coli* and the application of that group of antibiotics in poultry farming, and that correlation can be used to measure the risks of abusive utilization of antimicrobials in farming of aviary cultures, and be useful for international governments in the creation of legislations that control the distribution of those medications. The investigation focus is to demonstrate the health risks of the exaggerated application of tetracycline in poultry farming, and how the resistance developed by

the *E. Coli* in aviary cultures can be harmful to human beings.

In feeding plans of poultry developed antibiotic resistant *E. Coli* over time, due to the family of tetracycline antibiotics being the second most used medication in livestock farming in Europe, corresponding to 25,8% of sales[ESVAC] and the single most used one in the United States, corresponding to 67% of sales[FDA]. The *E. Coli* that is exposed to the antibiotic will develop resistance due to replication and inheritance of resistant genes, that may happen via Transduction, term that defines a :”bacteriophage-mediated transfer of DNA from one cell (a donor) to another cell (a recipient)” (Birge,1) , via Conjugation, defined by the “horizontal gene transfer mechanism through which DNA is transferred from a donor to a recipient bacterium by direct contact” (Virolle,1) , or Transformation, process defined by “one mode of horizontal gene transfer (HGT) in bacteria, wherein extracellular naked DNA is taken up by cells that have developed genetic competence” (Hasegawa,1) . Resistant bacteria can transfer the developed resistant genetic traces through those means, creating an inheritance of those genes and developing more generations that are resistant to the antimicrobial. The resistant bacteria may infect humans when there is physical contact to the animals that are contaminated with the resistant pathogens, thus leading to infections on humans that can be further identified in the blood and urine canals of the organism, that are the most common ways of finding bacteria in the human body (Li, Wei et al, 2) . Those individuals that live in countries where the use of antibiotics in poultry farming and livestock are the most expressive will have the most clinical cases of infections caused by resistant bacteria to the most used antimicrobials in poultry and livestock feeding, leading to possible casualties originating from infections.

1.2 Null Hypothesis

The intensive use of tetracycline in poultry farming for any uses does not affect the development of drug resistant *E. Coli* through inheritance of antibiotic resistant genes by inheritance, thus not increasing the number of clinical cases related to resistant bacterial

infections caused by AR microorganisms. The decrease in clinical infections from resistant pathogens will prevent any risk of infection to humans, thus not generating any potential casualties.

2. Methods

The research was focused on prioritizing the data sets of antimicrobial usage specifically in poultry farming in specific countries, those countries being the same found in the demographic of infections caused by antibiotic resistant bacteria. The method of research is summarized in funneling the countries found in the first database, (usage of tetracycline in poultry farming [ESVAC], use of general antibiotics in livestock, use of general antibiotics in poultry farming [ESVAC] and number of infections caused by resistant pathogens found in blood specimens of humans[WHO GLASS]. The WHO GLASS database also provided the number of infections discovered via urine specimens, but due to being easier for health institutions to detect infections that way, some countries had astronomical numbers for the statistic, which made crafting data impossible, because some countries would had up to 20 times more infections than the others in the database. With that , the statistic was not considered for further data. Using the information provided to further research into specific data sources of infections caused by resistant bacteria given by the selected countries chosen in the first database. After the collection of data from all countries highlighted, sets of the data gathered would be builded into statistical data such as graphs and diagrams to find if the use of tetracycline affect or not the development of resistant *E. Coli* infections in humans. The average amount of tetracycline bought in each country selected will also be investigated through the European Surveillance of Veterinary Antimicrobial Consumption (ESVAC) being measured in (mg/PCU), which stands for Population Correction Unit, a unit of measurement created by the European Medicines Agency to monitor the usage of antimicrobials and sales of it per population of animals [VETERINARY MEDICINES DIRECTORATE]. It is valuable to clarify that the usage in poultry and the amount bought may correlate in different ways, those countries in which there is a heavy usage of tetracycline in poultry farming and an

constant supply of it being bought each year and countries where there isn't a heavy usage of tetracycline directed specifically to poultry farming but the country buys a heavy supply of the antibiotic yearly. This may affect the data built due to the diversity of functions that tetracycline perform in many different cultures (Granados-Chinchilla et al., 4-6).

3. Data Analysis

Due to the insufficient amount of data relating to the exact consumption of antimicrobials over the years by an reliable organization, the data collected for the topic needed to be matched with the number of infected patients provided by the World Health Organization (WHO), via the GLASS database for antimicrobial resistance related infections (Global Antimicrobial Resistance and Use Surveillance System (GLASS) Report. (n.d.)). The WHO GLASS

Table 1. Correlation of Infections Caused by AR *E. Coli* (WHO GLASS) and Usage of Antibiotics in Livestock. Data gathered from the ESVAC database.

Entity	Country	Antibiotic use in livestock (mg/PCU)	Total Number of Infections caused by resistant E.Coli (WHO GLASS 2021)	Number of Infections found in Blood Specimen (WHO GLASS 2021)
AUS	Austria	50.7	2382	2382
CRO	Croatia	101.6	143	143
CYP	Cyprus	434.2	60	60
CZE	Czechia	68.1	95	95
FIN	Finland	20.4	1494	1494
FRA	France	70.2	1264	1264
GER	Germany	97.6	1981	1981
GRE	Greece	57.2	1946	1946
ICE	Iceland	5	885	885
ITA	Italy	322	8356	8356
LTU	Lithuania	35.1	439	439
LUX	Luxembourg	34.6	38	38
NED	Netherlands	64.4	7300	7300
NOR	Norway	2.9	1106	1106
POL	Poland	138.9	75	75
SWE	Sweden	11.8	1069	1069
CHE	Switzerland	50.6	63	63
UK	United Kingdom	45	1932	1932

With the data found in **Table 1**, some arguments can be drawn about the analysis. It is notable that the correlation of infections caused by AR *E. Coli* (WHO GLASS) and usage of antibiotics in livestock in the 19 listed countries (ESVAC 2015) equals $r = 0.254$ meaning that the dataset crafted weakly correlates. The given databases were found in research by searching the terms of “infections caused by resistant bacteria in Europe” and “antibiotic use per European country”, both found in Google. The significance of

the Pearson Correlation Coefficient, represented by the equation :

$$r = \frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})(y - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2 \sum(y - \bar{y})^2}}$$

Calculated using a Texas Instruments TI-84 Plus, is to show if the data has an statistical relationship, by associating the result with a correlation.

The datasets vary from no correlation whatsoever, ($0 < r < 0.25$), if they had a weak correlation ($0.25 < r < 0.5$), if they presented a medium correlation ($0.5 < r < 0.75$) or if they presented a strong correlation ($0.75 < r < 1$) (Belcher. et al., 265). This statistic

shows that using antibiotics in livestock can indirectly cause slight development of antibiotic resistance in cultures, shown in the **Graph 1**, where the slight correlation was plotted.

Graph 1. Correlation of Antibiotic use in Livestock x Number of infections caused by AR *E. Coli*

As mentioned previously, **Graph 1** shows the slight correlation of both datasets, with the exception of some outliers, that are represented in **Table 1**. Those outliers differentiate in both axis, due to the trend being applicable for most of the countries where a correlation exists. The outlier data are countries that the antibiotic use go beyond the mean of the dataset by an extreme margin ($\bar{x} = 89.47$ mg/PCU, antibiotic use in Cyprus = 434.2 mg/PCU) but has a low number of AR infections (N° of infections in Cyprus = 60), countries with an application of antimicrobials close to the mean ($\bar{x} = 89.47$ mg/PCU, antibiotic use in Netherlands = 64.4 mg/PCU) and a very high number of infections (N° of infections in Netherlands = 7300) and countries with both extreme above average use of medication in livestock ($\bar{x} = 89.47$ mg/PCU, antibiotic use in resistant *E. Coli*, because the resistant bacteria may not originate from livestock means and from other means, resulting in a high number of infections where country. The country is ranked 8th in the highest livestock population in the European Union [EUROSTAT DATABASE], explaining the need for a high demand of antimicrobials for the population. With the high use of the medications, there is a

Italy = 322 mg/PCU) and very high number of infections (N° of infections in Italy = 8356). The other countries represented have correlated data, where the antibiotic use is slightly correspondent to the number of infections. Cyprus, Netherlands and Italy, respectively, are the outliers for the situations described. The situation observed in Cyprus can be explained by an high number of LSU (Livestock Unit) per capita of 0.239 [EUROSTAT], found by dividing the number of livestock units of 207500 units in the country and the total population of 1187280 people [WORLD BANK] in the year where the infections were recorded (2015), which may result in a need of more antibiotics for the livestock population. The statistics found in the Netherlands can be explained by the diverse nature of

the usage of antimicrobials are uncorrelated and below the expected correlation. Italy data can be nitidly explained by certain information of the window for the development of resistant *E. Coli* in the livestock animals. A also important note is that undercooked meat is a common dish in Italian cuisine, and the consumption of it from non-quality sources may result in the proliferation of resistant

bacteria in the human organism, resulting in possible infections.

Graph 2. Use of Antibiotics in livestock (mg/PCU) x Infections Caused by AR *E. Coli*

Graph 2 represents the data from **Table 1** in a simplified manner, where it is understandable and shown that the number of infections is somehow corresponding to how much antimicrobials are used in the farming of livestock in each country. The presence of outliers are even more highlighted, those being Cyprus, Italy and Netherlands. It is also notable to mention the presence of data that do not correlate, but not by an extensive margin such as the described

before. Those datasets are described where the consumption of antibiotics were slightly below the average of $\bar{x} = 89.47 \text{ mg/PCU}$, but the number of infections were almost null. Take example of Czechia, where the usage of antimicrobials were slightly below the average ($\bar{x} = 89.47 \text{ mg/PCU}$, *Antibiotic use in Czechia = 68.1 mg/PCU*) and the country registered only 95 infections caused by AR *E. Coli*.

Table 2. Table analyzing the use of tetracycline, measured in mg/PCU, and its correlation with the number of infections caused by AR *E. Coli*. Data gathered from the ESVAC database.

Entity	Country	Year	Sales of Tetracyclines for food-producing animals (mg/PCU) (ESVAC)	Total Number of Infections caused by resistant E.Coli (WHO)	Number of Infections found in Blood Specimen (WHO GLASS)	Ratio of Tetracyclines sales x Infections caused by AR E.coli
AUS	Austria	2015	20.41	2382	2382	0.00857
CRO	Croatia	2015	21.02	143	143	0.147
CYP	Cyprus	2015	113.43	60	60	1.8905
CZE	Czechia	2015	12.77	95	95	0.13442
FIN	Finland	2015	3.61	1494	1494	0.00242
FRA	France	2015	16.62	1264	1264	0.01316
GER	Germany	2015	15.47	1981	1981	0.00781
GRE	Greece	2015	57.31	1946	1946	0.0295
ICE	Iceland	2015	0.46	885	885	0.00052
ITA	Italy	2015	40.33	8356	8356	0.00483
LTU	Lithuania	2015	2.77	439	439	0.00631
LUX	Luxembourg	2015	4.08	38	38	0.1074
NED	Netherlands	2015	16.19	7300	7300	0.00222
NOR	Norway	2015	0.04	1106	1106	0.000036
POL	Poland	2015	36.86	75	75	0.4915
SWE	Sweden	2015	0.92	1069	1069	0.00086
CHE	Switzerland	2015	6.91	63	63	0.1097
UK	United Kingdom	2015	9.58	1932	1932	0.00496

The data from **Table 2** analyzes the use of tetracycline, one of the most widely applied antibiotics in poultry farming and in livestock and also one of the antibiotics that *E. Coli* is most resistant to (Agyare et al.,37) a. The data analyzed was gathered from the ESVAC database, measured in mg/PCU, and it was correlated with the number of infections caused by AR *E. Coli* from the WHO GLASS database, aiming to test a correlation between datasets. The result of the Pearson

Correlation Coefficient was $r = 0.057$, meaning that the datasets don't show any correlation. **Table 2** also gives information about the ratio of tetracycline Sales and Number of Infections, which can be useful to understand what countries are most affected by antimicrobial resistance of *E. Coli* and which one has the most sales per infection and serve as a parameter to what countries are affected the most by the use of tetracycline. The shown correlation shall be plotted into a scatter graph, shown in **Graph 3**.

Graph 3. Correlation of Tetracyclines Sales and Number of Infections Caused by AR *E. Coli*

Graph 3 plots the data correlation into a scatter graph, where the result of the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of $r = 0.057$ is visible through the lack of any relation that the points have to each other. The lack of correlation is even more supported by the presence of three outliers. The outliers are the same from **Table 1** and **Graph 1**, and for the same outline data. The countries that differ from the dataset are Cyprus, Netherlands and Italy. Cyprus has a tetracycline use much higher than the mean use of it, ($\bar{x} = 21.04 \text{ mg/PCU}$, tetracycline use in Cyprus = 113.43 mg/PCU) but a very low number of infections still (N° of infections in Cyprus = 60). The Netherlands has a tetracycline use below the average for the 19 countries analyzed ($\bar{x} = 21.04 \text{ mg/PCU}$, tetracycline use in The Netherlands = 16.19 mg/PCU), however there is alarming rate of infections still for infections caused by AR *E. Coli* (N° of infections in Netherlands = 7300). Italy has correlation between its sets, for the reason that both are at very high numbers in the dataset, being the

third country at uses the most tetracycline ($\bar{x} = 21.04 \text{ mg/PCU}$, tetracycline use in Italy = 40.33 mg/PCU) and the 1st N° of infections (N° of infections in Italy = 8356). The other countries present in the dataset also don't follow any correlation, explained by the Pearson value of $r = 0.057$.

4. Discussion

With all the data displayed, it is possible to find if the objective of the investigation was fulfilled and which of the proposed hypotheses were correct. The aim of the research was to find if the use of the antibiotic class of tetracycline in poultry farming affects the proliferation of AR (antibiotic resistant) *E. Coli* to humans. Data was collected between the ESVAC database and the WHO GLASS database, to investigate whether there is a correlation between the use of general antibiotics in livestock farming with the number of infections caused by antibiotic

resistant *E. Coli*. The two sets were displayed into a table (**Table 1**) and a graph (**Graph 1**) to demonstrate the hypothesis. This dataset was chosen for the reason that analyzing whether antibiotics applied in excessive amounts in livestock could provoke the spread of antibiotic resistance through further generations of *E. Coli*, potentially leading to clinical infections caused by resistant bacteria. After collecting the data, the Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was calculated to identify if the two datasets had any correlation. The objective of finding (r) was to discover whether an excessive usage of antibiotics in livestock farming did not increase,

For the progress of the research, it is necessary to analyze the usage of the tetracycline class of antibiotics in general livestock, which could affect poultry farming. As seen in **Table 2**, which represented the use of tetracycline found in the ESVAC database and the number of infections originated from AR *E. Coli* from the WHO GLASS database, the raw data was processed to demonstrate if a correlation between the two sets existed or not. The choice of tetracycline for the analysis was for the reason that the class of tetracycline are the most used antibiotics in livestock in most of the farming countries of the world, such as the United States [FDA], and this expressive use should impact the rate of AR *E. Coli* infections according to the hypothesis. With that, it was interesting for the aim of the investigation to calculate the Pearson Correlation Coefficient of the datasets. The $r = 0.057$, which, as mentioned before, means that the two sets of data don't show any correlation whatsoever, and that the use of tetracycline in livestock does not affect the development of tetracycline resistant *E. Coli* in the human population. A possible explanation for this fact is that some countries may prioritize other antimicrobials in livestock, in which the bacteria may acquire resistance to it. Countries with low tetracycline usage, as demonstrated in **Table 1**, and high number of infections caused by AR bacteria are an example of this circumstance, such as the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden and Lithuania. These and other outliers may have affected the correlation between datasets and showed that both data do not have any relation, which means that the hypothesis has to be rejected. This lack of any correlation is shown in **Graph 3**.

slightly increase, moderately increase or strongly increase the number of infections caused by the AR bacteria. The result of (r) was equal to $r = 0.254$, meaning that the usage of antimicrobials in general livestock farming slightly correlated with the number of infections caused by the AR bacteria. The conclusion that can be proposed from this data is that even though the number is not alarming, there shall be a concern with health authorities in the countries listed in the data, due to potential biological damage that the excessive use of antimicrobials could cause in humans.

5. Evaluation

It is possible to evaluate a few setbacks that were found during the research process that if solved would add considerably to the analysis. One of which is the lack of data for the use of tetracyclines specifically in poultry cultures, that if found would enrich the argument presented and add value to the data. The lack of data for more countries, such as Caribbean, African and South American countries for both datasets presented were a step back to represent the theme as a global concern, because the rise of antibiotic resistance is a worldwide issue.

6. Conclusion

With all the data processed and analyzed, it is possible to draw a conclusion to where the aim of the research was fulfilled and whether hypotheses best fit the results achieved with the research. The research focused on investigating the relationship between the application of tetracyclines in poultry farming and the number of AR *E. Coli* infections in human populations. However, due to the lack of data on the specific usage of tetracyclines in poultry cultures, the use of the antimicrobial in livestock populations across 19 countries and their respective number of infections was used as a parameter, due to the variety of functions that tetracyclines can perform in a wide diversity of cultures. The results showed no correlation between antibiotics and infections in humans, shown in the analysis of **Table 2**. The analysis of **Table 1**, even though it may differ from the focus of the research, has its importance to the

scientific community, because the data present in **Table 1**, being the usage of general antibiotics in general livestock farming and the number of infections caused by AR *E. Coli* had shown a slight correlation. Even though the application of antimicrobials in the E.U is being more monitored and strict, it should be of concern to health authorities, for the reason that the datasets analyzed shows that when more antimicrobials are used in general livestock, the more likely is to bacteria in the animals develop resistance due to high doses and the resistant pathogen infecting a human being, in which is not likely to have treatment available for the resistant bacteria. In conclusion, the application of general antibiotics in livestock is a classic dilemma in the scientific community, due to the growing heed provoked by the potential harm that AR bacteria can cause in the development of new medications that counter bacterial organisms. The sales and dosages of antimicrobials shall be even more carefully monitored by health authorities across the globe, to prevent global outbreaks of drug-resistant pathogens. The use of tetracyclines, although not quite harmful to humans, should be of concern to health authorities if the number of antibiotics sold have a substantial rise, because it may affect human health due to how easy it is for *E. Coli* to develop resistance to this specific class of antibiotics.

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